

Juvenile Travellers: Priscilla Wakefield's Excursions in Empire

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While most discussions of juvenile imperial literature relate to the mid-nineteenth century onwards, this article draws attention to an earlier period by examining the children's books of Priscilla Wakefield. Between 1794 and 1817 Priscilla Wakefield wrote sixteen children's books that included moral tales, natural history books and a popular travel series. Her experience of the British Empire's territories was, in the main, derived from the work of others but her use of interesting characters, exciting travel scenarios, the epistolary form to enhance the narrative and fold-out maps, added interest to the information she presented. Her strong personal beliefs are evident throughout her writing and an abhorrence of slavery is a recurring theme. She was also the grandmother and main caregiver of the young Edward Gibbon Wakefield and his immediate siblings. In contrast to his grandmother, Edward Gibbon Wakefield's experience of the empire was both theoretical and practical. He drew on, and departed from, the work of political economists to develop his theory of systematic colonisation and was active in both Canadian and New Zealand affairs. He began writing about colonisation in the late 1820s and his grandmother's influence can be seen in his wide use of existing sources and attractive writing style to communicate with his audience.

Based on the premise, 'that juvenile literature acts as an excellent reflector of the dominant ideas of an age',¹ the main focus of this article is to present a study of books of Priscilla Wakefield (née Bell) (1751-1832) to determine the view of the British Empire and its territories that she conveyed to the child reader. Priscilla Wakefield had a major role in the upbringing of her grandchildren and this article will argue that the style, content and personal beliefs reflected in Priscilla's children's books were an influential force in their lives.

To date, most of the interest in the relationship between children's literature and empire has focussed on a period beginning in the mid-nineteenth century. This is a reflection of the emergence of new genres, 'the domestic tale for girls and the empire-building adventure stories for boys'.² At the time Priscilla began writing, in the 1790s, the American colonies had been lost and 'the imperial century' was still to begin. But, even so, 'at the end of the eighteenth century ... Britain was a major colonial power, with territorial possessions spread far and wide, in which there were a multitude of languages, customs and religions.'³ From an examination of her books we see that unlike later juvenile literature, Priscilla's view of empire did not reflect one of glorious conquest over geographical areas of the globe, but one that was more benign and strongly tempered by ideas of morality and social justice focussed at the level of the individual.

Priscilla did not travel widely she only undertook short journeys to London or to visit family members. Her knowledge of Britain's territories was derived mainly from the written work of others. But an appreciation of her influential position in the Wakefield family throws new light on some of the views and actions of other family members who did become active participants in colonial affairs. Within a generation, the Wakefield family would be intimately involved with colonisation schemes, from both theoretical and practical perspectives. Of particular interest to this study are her grandsons, the colonial theorist Edward Gibbon Wakefield (1796-1862) and to a lesser extent his brothers Arthur Wakefield (1799-1843) and William Hayward Wakefield (1801-1848).

From about 1830 on, Edward Gibbon embarked on a personal crusade to promote his theory of systematic colonisation. Before this time, in his view, 'there [was] long experience without a system, immense results without a plan, vast doings but no principles.'⁴ Drawing on current economic, social and political ideas systematic colonisation was a new approach to deal with Britain's rapidly increasing population by establishing colonies where the sale of

land was regulated by a 'sufficient price'. Edward Gibbon's ideas, underpinned by his forceful personality, undoubtedly influenced mid-nineteenth century colonial policy and the development of Canada, Australia and New Zealand.

As the Wakefield family, like so many others in the nineteenth century, scattered across the empire it would be New Zealand where Edward Gibbon, four of his brothers, his son and other family members would ultimately end their days.⁵ In New Zealand's colonial history Edward Gibbon Wakefield is a man whose contribution remains contentious. Attitudes towards him have swung between veneration and vilification as each generation has re-examined its historical beginnings. This variation in opinion is evident, not only over time, but also from opposite sides of the globe.⁶ Although dismissed by some New Zealand historians, the legacy of the New Zealand Company and the Wakefield family linger on and occasionally re-emerge as a touchstone element in the nation's story.⁷

Priscilla Wakefield lived the greater part of her life in Tottenham, Middlesex, in close proximity to her extended Quaker family. Although a Quaker throughout her life, she did not embrace some of its more restrictive practices. As the eldest of ten children she was closely involved with the education of her younger siblings. In the introduction to one of her later works she wrote:

I am the eldest daughter of a very numerous family, and received my education in the paternal house, under the inspection of one of the most excellent of mothers, to whose incessant care and admirable example, I owe the foundation of any merit I may possess. From my earliest years she taught me the habit of industry, and employed me, whilst a child, to assist her in instructing my younger sisters.⁸

In 1771 Priscilla married Edward Wakefield, a London merchant. The couple lived in London for over twenty years and during that time they had three children, Isabella, Edward and Daniel. In the early 1790s she began a writing career and soon after, the family left London to return to Tottenham. It is believed the motivation for Priscilla's writing was the family's financial difficulties brought about by husband Edward's lack of business sense.⁹ Priscilla's journals, for the years 1796 to 1816, enumerated Edward's various business ventures and the financial and family problems that usually ensued.¹⁰ Throughout her life she undertook many philanthropic activities including the development of the first English savings bank and laying-in charities for poor expectant mothers.¹¹

Writing and publication, often combined with an interest in social change, was an intergenerational activity in the Wakefield family. Priscilla takes a central position within a family literary continuum that began with her great-grandfather, Robert Barclay, who wrote the Quaker *Apology for the True Christian Divinity* and extended to her son, grandson and great-grandson.¹² Between 1794 and 1817 she wrote sixteen books for children and one for an adult audience. Her views on children's education, particularly that of girls, the anti-slavery movement and the study of the natural world have attracted an increasing amount of scholarly interest.¹³ However, an examination of a single volume does not reveal her personal writing journey from the didactic to the travel book. Nor does it place her within the context of the wider Wakefield family literary background or expose her influence on subsequent generations.

Priscilla Wakefield was one of a number of women writers of children's books in the late eighteenth century. Gillian Avery states that before 1780 children's books were often written by publishers themselves, 'but from that year, quite spontaneously, the professional writer took over and juvenile literature began in earnest.'¹⁴ A new interest in children's

education, influenced by theorists such as Locke and Rousseau, generated a market for books that was filled by this group of ‘scribblers for children’.¹⁵

With the exception of authors such as Sarah Trimmer and Maria Edgeworth the majority of the early writers of children’s books have faded into obscurity. However, the influence a writer such as Priscilla may have had on other similarly pious and home educated authors such as the Strickland sisters or the prolific Charlotte Yonge, should not be underestimated.¹⁶ Within the arena of children’s literature Priscilla has been considered a minor author because, as F. J. Harvey Darton notes, ‘she wrote little fiction, but strung together historical and similar stories’.¹⁷ Of the children’s books written at this time Avery makes the following assessment:

In one or two of the hundreds of dry little books produced between 1780 and 1820 by this dedicated horde of female writers can be detected the faint flickering of imagination, the pale shadow of the real child. But for the most part they are not attempting to write about children at all, they are presenting personifications of the very good or the very wicked ... their works can rarely be considered fiction.¹⁸

While it is correct that Priscilla gleaned the factual basis of her books from existing sources, the family scenarios she devised to overlay the information and the way she creatively progressed a narrative has received little attention. In considering Priscilla’s works it is useful to take a chronological view and appreciate the changes in her writing over her entire career as some of the features of her books are better understood in this wider context.

Her sixteen children’s books can be grouped into three types; moral tales, natural history and travel books. At first she wrote several moral tales followed by a book on botany and just before the turn of the century her only book for an adult audience, *Reflections on the Present Condition of the Female Sex*. In 1801 she wrote the first of the travel books *The*

Juvenile Travellers. It was also her most popular, and over the next twenty years a total of six travel books were interspersed with moral tales and instructional scientific works.

After her early success with the didactic form she appeared to gain more confidence as a writer and developed her own style. In the travel series she made her books attractive to the child reader by inventing characters, devising interesting scenarios and including letters and journals in the text. Each book has a folded map of the relevant area of the world inside the front cover with the journey of the characters shown on the map. To reinforce the idea that the journey had actually been undertaken an itinerary was sometimes included. The natural history books on botany and insects are illustrated with delightful paintings, often in colour, that we can assume were done by Priscilla herself. In line with her personal beliefs the books 'are imbued with a Friendly spirit',¹⁹ the abolition of slavery, religious toleration and equality being strong themes throughout.

Priscilla Wakefield's first book *Leisure Hours*²⁰ was published in two volumes with the first in 1794. The title page of the first volume of *Leisure Hours* gives the author as only Priscilla **** with no surname but all later works did carry her full name. Its publication slightly pre-dates Priscilla's move from London to Tottenham and it also coincides with the birth of Priscilla's first grandchild Catherine in 1793. Catherine, (the eldest of what would be ten children) was the child of Priscilla's son Edward who married in 1791 at the age of seventeen. Over the next decade and beyond Priscilla's life would be dominated by long periods of caring for her grandchildren while writing and coping with various family and financial difficulties.

Leisure Hours consisted of over forty short stories designed to provide the child with a moral lesson or didactic. The reader was presented with a short introduction to place an event in its historical context followed by a conversation or dialogue between the characters

where one of them learnt a good lesson. In the preface it is stated the dialogues were intentionally left open-ended to provide an opportunity for further discussion between children and parents, the aim being, ‘rather to excite, than gratify the curiosity’.²¹

The moral lessons draw heavily on classical literature and stories of kings and nobility but of interest to this investigation is the story titled the ‘Petition of Gayashuta’.²² It began with the well known address of a North American Indian chief to the descendants of William Penn, a Quaker and founder of Pennsylvania. This story is quite different from the other dialogues. The reason for its inclusion being, ‘the beauty, simplicity, and persuasive eloquence of the following original composition, (communicated to me by a friend,) is the only apology I shall offer for giving it a place among these Dialogues, though differing from them in form.’²³ The Speech of Gayashuta described, in a positive way, the relationship of Penn with the indigenous population. Following the address, Priscilla added that Penn was held in high regard by the Indian people because of the way he treated them and although land had been legally granted to Penn his relationship with them was dictated by ‘his integrity and justice, which he manifested in every transaction with them, distaining to take a mean advantage of their ignorance or weakness, but fairly purchased those lands they were willing to spare’.²⁴

Penn received an early mention in the book *Excursions in North America* published in 1806. This was the third of Priscilla’s travel books, but the first that took the characters Henry Franklin and his young companion Arthur Middleton into a colonial environment. In the travel books Arthur Middleton becomes the main character and over the duration of the series he ages from fourteen years old in 1804 to maturity in the final 1817 book. In a fictional letter Henry Franklin in Pennsylvania writes about William Penn’s ‘upright and generous treatment of the Indians from whom he made the purchase’ and because of their confidence in Penn ‘to this day, they are never perfectly satisfied with any treaty, unless some Quakers are present at

the conference ; for, say they, the descendants of William Penn will never suffer us to be deceived'.²⁵

Penn's personal and religious convictions were qualities highlighted by Priscilla. She made a number of references to him in her books and in 1816 wrote *A Brief Memoir of the Life of William Penn*. She detailed the facts of his life including his conversion to Quakerism, the time spent in Newgate Prison, his acquisition of Pennsylvania and successful governorship. It will be argued that the example of William Penn was particularly influential on Priscilla's grandchildren Edward Gibbon and William Wakefield in their interest in colonisation and interactions with indigenous people particularly in New Zealand.

An Introduction to Botany was the first of Priscilla's books on natural history and also the first time she used the epistolary form, as the text consisted of an exchange of letters between the sisters Felicia and Constance. The epistolary style was popular in the eighteenth century with the success of authors such as Samuel Richardson and Henry Fielding. For Priscilla it became a favourite, one that she used in her natural history and travel books. Some books included letters within the text exchanged between single or multiple characters while others consisted entirely of letters.

In *Mental Improvement* Priscilla introduced another feature, a family set of characters and their related friends. The Harcourt family consisted of Mr and Mrs Harcourt, children Sophia, Cecelia, Charles, Henry and a visiting child Augusta. The aim of the book was to encourage the development of observation by presenting information about everyday objects in a series of dialogues between the characters. Topics ranged widely from salmon, shells, glass and wool with discussions on their origin and domestic use.

This is the first example in her books of Priscilla's opposition to the slave trade, an issue that was of particular concern to Quakers. The abolition message is a strong theme that

runs throughout the remainder of Priscilla's children's books.²⁶ The issue of the origin of West Indian sugar prompts a detailed description of the realities of the slave trade by Mr and Mrs Harcourt. They explain the production of sugar from the West Indies is undertaken by negro slaves who are, 'natives of Africa, but snatched from their own country, friends, and connections, by the hand of violence and power'.²⁷ Shocked by the information imparted by his parents Charles, aged fifteen, exclaims, 'my indignation arises at this recital. Why does not the British parliament exert its power, to avenge the wrongs of these oppressed Africans? What can prevent an act being passed to forbid Englishmen from buying and selling slaves?'²⁸ Cecilia, aged twelve, resolves 'I think no riches could tempt me to have and share in the slave-trade. I could never enjoy peace of mind, whilst I thought I contributed to the woes of my fellow-creatures.'²⁹ As a result of the discussion all the children decide to forgo sugar, coffee, rice, calico and other products produced by slave labour.

The publication of *Mental Improvement* coincided with a major slave-grown sugar boycott of the early 1790s where women took a leading role. The conversation in the Harcourt household reflected the domestic scenes that took place during the abstention campaign and described by Midgley as the 'cultural politics of the tea-table'.³⁰ The moral stance taken by the Harcourt family extended beyond West Indian sugar to a wider range of goods. This focussed the reader on the central message that distant countries could be the source of useful products, but the use of slavery as a means of their production was abhorrent.

In 1798 Priscilla published her only book for an adult audience, *Reflections on the Present Condition of the Female Sex*. It was one of a number of books written on the role of women initiated by Mary Wollstonecraft's 1792 *A Vindication of the Rights of Women*. The book does not appear to have been well received. Priscilla wrote in her journal, 'my spirit for writing a little damped by hearing that the "British Critic" has treated my "Reflections" with

slight if not contempt, suggesting it refers only to Female Education'.³¹ She did not return to that genre again.

At the turn of century Priscilla was burdened by numerous family disputes and crippling financial problems that were compounded by the dependence of her son Edward and increasingly ill daughter-in-law to care for their children. Her role resembled more a mother, than a grandmother, she 'seems to have taken "complete charge of her elder two grandchildren ... for a considerable period"'.³² The competing demands of family and writing are evident in her journal entry of 24 October 1802: 'stayed at home with the children, find two much heavier charge than one. Fear my reading and writing must be sacrificed for the next three months at least, but hope to return in that time some essential benefit to my dear little boy, whose extreme habits of liberty at home increase the difficulty of orderly restraint.'³³ The boy was six year old grandson Edward Gibbon whose behaviour throughout childhood and beyond would be the source of much concern to his grandmother.

The poor reception of *Reflections* seems to have brought a new direction to Priscilla's writing. To the didactic and nature study she added the travel book that would develop into a series. *The Juvenile Travellers* was the first and most popular of all the travel books.³⁴ The main characters are the English Seymour family consisting of Mr and Mrs Seymour and their children, Theodore and Laura, who go on an extended tour of Europe. The aim of the publication was a travel book that was suitable for children. Inside the front cover was a folded map of Europe showing the various routes taken by the characters and the child reader could also engage with the fictional scenario through the inclusion of letters and itineraries.³⁵ The tour began in Copenhagen and after the family have explored the city Mr Seymour takes Theodore on a separate journey to Sweden leaving his wife and daughter behind.

This is the first example in Priscilla's books where she devises a situation to physically separate the characters so they can write letters to each other describing their experiences.³⁶ Laura also befriended Sophia, the daughter of an English merchant, who continued on a separate journey with the two girls corresponding throughout the book. The separation of the characters within the narrative and the use of letters as a form of descriptive communication between them became a feature of her travel books. The separation of the male and female characters in *The Juvenile Travellers* and *A Family Tour* have gained attention from Labbe and Kroeg for reinforcing early nineteenth century gender roles.³⁷ The character of Laura Seymour in *The Juvenile Travellers* is a notable exception. When her brother Theodore is believed to be dead, Laura is given greater opportunities to travel, learn and spend time with her father than she had at the beginning of the journey.³⁸ This freedom for a female character is not repeated in other travel books and as their content encompassed more of the globe the central characters of the active journey are male.³⁹ In subsequent books it is only the central character Arthur Middleton, accompanied by various male friends, who ventured overseas and related his experiences through letters or journals to his mother and siblings in England.

A Family Tour through the British Empire was published in 1804 and like *The Juvenile Travellers*, the narrative consists of a combination of geographical, historical and biographical information overlaid by the family tour scenario. Priscilla created the Middleton's a new family that would feature in the remainder of the travel books. The fictional family consisted of a widow, Mrs Middleton and her four children, Catherine eleven years, Louisa nine, Arthur fourteen and Edwin thirteen. Could these characters be based on three of the four older Wakefield grandchildren? ⁴⁰ At the time of publication, the eldest Wakefield grandchild was Catherine also aged eleven, Edward Gibbon (Edwin?) was eight and Arthur five years old. Between the brothers Edward Gibbon and Arthur was Daniel, born

in 1798, but his fictional counterpart is excluded from the Middleton family in favour of a female character, Louisa. This balanced the sex ratio of the fictional Middleton family. But in the Wakefield family, the three year gap between the birth of Catherine and her brother Edward Gibbon, suggests a baby that may have died and could provide some insight into the early life and subsequent personality of an over indulged first-born son. And does Priscilla cast herself as Mrs Middleton, a woman free from the constraints of a husband?

In *A Family Tour through the British Empire*, Mrs Middleton, in the company of Mr Franklin the boys' tutor undertakes a tour of the recently unified Kingdom of Great Britain and Ireland. The union of both kingdoms, states Mr Franklin, 'is expected to promote the general happiness of the whole, and should destroy all national distinctions, and unite the members of the British empire into one vast brotherhood, endeared by the most friendly offices and the mutual ties of interest'.⁴¹ Priscilla's use of 'British Empire' in the title of her book reflects the recent nature of the unification that had occurred just three years earlier. In the following travel books, where Arthur visits North America, Africa and Asia, Priscilla uses the word 'empire' to describe the territories or colonies of other countries. She does not use the term British Empire for the wider relationship between the metropole and its territories. The closest she comes is 'British territories' in her last book *The Traveller in Asia* published in 1817.⁴²

In 1806, after taking her readers on tours of Europe and the United Kingdom, Priscilla's attention turned to the North American continent in the book *Excursions in North America*. The preface stating, 'the variety of natural productions in North America, both animal and vegetable, and the connection it formerly had with this country, give it a peculiar claim to the notice of British youth'.⁴³ Arthur Middleton, a character from *A Family Tour of the British Empire*, who is described as showing a 'disposition for an active life and a desire for novelty',⁴⁴ travels to North America as the companion of Mr Henry Franklin. Franklin is

the brother of Arthur's tutor and according to Priscilla's scenario he was commissioned by a nobleman to explore North America and report on what he found.

The text consists of forty-five letters from Arthur and Henry home to respective family members. Along with her usual descriptive style this book has a strong focus on social issues; particularly slavery and the effect of European colonisation on indigenous people. Arthur's first encounter with slaves occurs when he attends a social function, Henry Franklin 'observed a cloud upon the brow of my young friend ... he confessed, that the sight of men, who were the property of their fellow creatures, and subject to every indignity, excited such painful reflections, that he could not banish them from his mind'.⁴⁵ Franklin reassures Arthur that in some states and amongst people such as the Quakers, negro slavery had now been abolished. The book identifies another form of bondage operating in America, white slavery, in which poor European labourers received a free passage in return to being sold to an employer for a number of years.

After these discussions, the character of an African slave Sancho is brought into the narrative. By creating Sancho, Priscilla was able to personalise the issues around slavery as opposed to general statements within the text. When Arthur and Henry attend a slave market they encounter a young man with a 'dejected countenance'⁴⁶ about to be sold and separated from his wife. Arthur wants to purchase the slave and give him his freedom while Henry Franklin reminds him of the 'insufficiency of redeeming an individual'.⁴⁷ But Henry relents and agrees on the practical basis of their need for a servant on their travels. When they complete their journey Sancho and his wife settle in Nantucket where he works as a cooper, 'a free man, and enjoying an independent right to whatever he may acquire by his industry'.⁴⁸ Arthur, Henry and Sancho are reunited at the end of *Excursions in North America* onboard a boat to Canton where Sancho plans to sell a cargo of sea-otter skins. Arthur is nearly attacked by a shark but is rescued in time by Sancho. This heroic act 'rendered their obligations equal'

and 'Sancho never forgot, observing the most respectful conduct towards his liberator; who, on his side, endeavoured, by every condescending attention, to diminish the distinction between them.'⁴⁹ At the end of *Excursions in North America* Sancho is a free man, settled and employed. Priscilla could have left him there as a positive example of abolition. But later Sancho is returned to Arthur's side in *The Traveller in Africa*. The older Sancho is now a widower and ultimately the story of the return to his homeland is not a happy one reflecting the destructive impact that slavery can have on the life of one individual.

In juvenile literature published later in the nineteenth century it has been argued that images of empire 'are by and large organized through such binary oppositions as self and other, civilised and savage, white and black'.⁵⁰ But throughout her books Priscilla seems at pains to promote the idea of the 'not other' and attempt to bridge differences in colour, culture and economic circumstance by focussing on shared human experiences. She takes this to another level in *The Traveller in Africa* when the central character of the travel series Arthur Middleton, along with Sancho, is captured into slavery by Arabs on the Western Coast of Africa. After collecting wood, churning butter and cooking meat for their master they are sold to a slave trader and taken with others to the city of Mogodore. Arthur believes he has secured their freedom by guaranteeing the repayment of their purchase price to a British merchant only to discover he was now the slave of the Moorish Emperor. Following a meeting with the Emperor and the presentation of gifts Arthur and Sancho are released from captivity to continue their journey. This outcome was not the reality for the many thousands of English, Welsh, Scottish and Irish captives who were seized by Barbary corsairs from the sixteenth century on.⁵¹ The anti-slavery message in her books had progressed from domestic discussions in 1794, to the development of Sancho in 1806, a character that was a victim of slavery, and finally in 1814 to the actual enslavement of her travel hero Arthur. Although

Britain abolished the transatlantic slave trade in 1807, Priscilla continued to place before her young readers the reality that other forms of human subjugation existed in the world.

In *Excursions in North America* young Arthur Middleton has many exciting adventures including narrow escapes from encounters with alligators and snakes. But he particularly wants ‘to visit the Indian nations that inhabit the interior of that extensive continent: he longed to see their warriors and partake with them the pursuits of their choice’.⁵² Large portions of the book are devoted to information about North American Indian tribes and Priscilla included more speeches from the Seneca chief Kayashota whom she introduced in her first book *Leisure Hours*. Described as ‘a chief of the Mohawks, who has had an European education, and to great natural talents adds the most admirable manners’. But that he, ‘sometimes speaks rather indignantly of the encroachments and arts, too often used by the European settlers, to diminish the territories of these, the native possessors of the soil’.⁵³

Priscilla is mildly critical of the colonisation activities of powerful European nations for whom ‘voyages of discovery became a kind of fashion’.⁵⁴ She has specific concerns about the character of some emigrants and their behaviour towards the indigenous people. Commenting that, ‘in the multitude of these emigrants, there are many unprincipled adventurers, who have no means of subsisting at home, and are therefore willing to seek a maintenance in a foreign country, where their character is not known.’⁵⁵ She argued that in North America these people isolated themselves in remote areas, built huts, cut down trees, planted crops and hunted game. When more Europeans arrived, these ‘borderers’ moved on to another area and pushed the Indian owners off their lands. Priscilla concluded ‘the number of Indians is said to diminish rapidly ; and it is thought that, in time, the white nations will become the sole possessors of the vast continent of America.’⁵⁶

Thirty years later, Edward Gibbon Wakefield's plan for systematic colonisation incorporated detailed proposals for the selection of emigrants, the management of land and capital and the geographical concentration of settlers. By following these principles he argued the Colony of South Australia would not become;

a Colony where immigration is left to chance or consists of the scum of the mother country, ... but ... a Colony founded on arrangements all of which are directed toward the production of the greatest and most rapid increase of its population, together with that degree of concentration which is most favourable to the progress in wealth.⁵⁷

In 1840 the New Zealand Company's first settlement was established in Wellington following the principles of systematic colonisation. Edward Gibbon's brother, William Hayward Wakefield acted as the Company's Principal Agent. The critical element of the plan was to purchase a large area of land from the indigenous Māori people for European settlement but to also reserve and hold in trust one-tenth for them. The rationale was, that without land being reserved, 'the danger to which [Māori] are exposed, and which they cannot foresee, is that of finding themselves entirely without landed property, and therefore without consideration, in the midst of a society where, through immigration and settlement, land has become a valuable property.'⁵⁸

This proposal emanated out of increasing concern in mid-nineteenth century Britain about the impact of colonisation on indigenous peoples⁵⁹ and echoed the concerns Priscilla had expressed in *Excursions in North America*. William Wakefield recognised that European concepts of land ownership were not recognised by Māori and he 'was accordingly obliged to buy of the natives, not certain lands within certain boundaries, but the rights, claims and interests of the contracting chieftains'.⁶⁰ The purchase of Wellington involved days of

discussions or *kōrero* between William and the Māori leaders that culminated in the drawing up and signing of a deed and payment in goods. These events, combined with the benevolent undertones hark back to the example of William Penn, Governor of Pennsylvania. This introduces the question of whether William Wakefield in his role as the founder of the European settlement in Wellington, saw himself in that old Quaker story. However, following the British annexation of New Zealand his status as an authority figure was diminished and the Company's land claims were subjected to a long government investigation. William Wakefield died suddenly in 1848 and his funeral was attended by European settlers and many hundreds of Māori who 'came to pay respect to a man whose ideas and actions they may have opposed but who carried the mana of a chief, had shown unwavering belief in his mission and had been a warrior of undoubted physical courage'.⁶¹

The *Sketches of Human Manners* was published in 1807 and consisted of a number of short stories from around the world and in the stories Priscilla emphasises human qualities common to all people. In 'The African Negro' a young man, who is devoted to his mother, is captured into slavery but escapes and undertakes an arduous journey home to discover his mother had died broken hearted. However, the significance of 'The Convict', in relation to actual events in the Wakefield family, resonates across two centuries of time. In the story a young man, William Harrison, is convicted of theft from his employer and is transported to New South Wales. He works with diligence and honesty gaining the trust of the authorities and eventually winning his freedom. He becomes a magistrate in the colony and decides to remain there rather than returning to England. At the end of the story the reader is told he had 'a well-spent life, respected and beloved by both the colonists and natives'.⁶²

In 1827, twenty years after the story was published, Priscilla's grandson Edward Gibbon was incarcerated in Newgate prison and served a three year sentence for abducting a wealthy young woman and marrying her without consent.⁶³ What childhood experiences

might have impacted on Edward Gibbon as he faced the consequences of his actions? The example of Quaker William Penn, also confined to Newgate on a number of occasions and who used the time to write religious tracts,⁶⁴ or the fictional convict William Harrison who made a new and respected life in the colonies?

From within the confines of a Newgate prison cell Edward Gibbon employed the lessons he had learnt at his grandmother's knee of reading widely, developing characters and a scenario, writing in a descriptive fashion and presenting information in an attractive format. Reading extensively on the subjects of transportation and colonisation, along with economic and political theory, Edward Gibbon developed what would become known as systematic colonisation. First introduced to the public anonymously in 1829, *A Letter from Sydney* was published in a serialised form in the *Morning Chronicle* newspaper. It was presented as a series of letters from a young gentleman recounting his experiences of New South Wales with suggestions for improvement, including a colonisation scheme. The familiar and conversational style of the letters led many people living in New South Wales to believe they were actually written in Australia. He even included Priscilla. The young man related a final visit to his grandmother:

Just before I embarked at Plymouth, I visited my grandmother, in order to take leave of her for ever. Poor old soul! she was already dead to the concerns of this life ... She shed an abundance of tears, and then became extremely curious to know every particular about the place to which I was going. I rubbed her spectacles whilst she wiped her eyes, and having placed before her a common English chart of the world, pointed out the situation of New Holland.⁶⁵

In the following narrative the grandmother becomes upset when she sees how far away the intended destination was from home. But the young man cuts the chart in half through

Iceland, transposes the parts laterally and turns it upside down asking ““where is England?” “Ah! boy,” she replied; “you may do what you like with the map ; but you can’t twist the world about in that manner, though they *are* making sad changes in it.””⁶⁶ For Edward Gibbon the conviction and sentence was a defining event that effectively closed many career options. But in Newgate Prison forces from his past would intersect and direct his reinvention as a reformer who would attempt to twist the colonial world in new directions.

In 1810 Priscilla was nearly sixty and her physical health began to decline. Her continuing ability to write provided some solace.

My health is in a very enfeebled state but with thankfulness I add that as far as I can judge my intellectual powers are unimpaired. I have published ‘Instinct Displayed’ and begun ‘Travels in Africa’[sic]. The employment of my writing is profitable, not only with a view to what it yields but also as an amusement, affording considerable relief from the cares of life.⁶⁷

Priscilla wrote in the preface of *The Traveller in Africa*, ‘from the great encouragement my attempts at describing different parts of the world have hitherto received. I feel greater confidence than I should otherwise do, in offering the public this imperfect sketch of these parts of Africa which have been visited by Europeans of credit.’⁶⁸ The map of Africa was engraved specifically for the book and based ‘on best authorities’. It shows six areas of the continent coloured in red presumably, those under British influence. Time has moved on for the Middleton family. Mrs Middleton has died, Louisa lives with the married Catherine, Edwin studies law but Arthur has a continuing desire to travel. He boards a ship for Africa and is joined by his friend Sancho, the slave he freed in *Excursions in North America*. Before his journey to Africa begins Arthur assures his family ‘that he was not led to direct his course to Africa by mere curiosity, but was animated by the hope of facilitating a communication

between the Africans and Europeans, that would be likely to promote the improvement and increase the comforts of the former, and prove beneficial for both.⁶⁹ The book consists of Arthur's long and often dense journal entries, but the book did include an index: a new feature for Priscilla's books. In the narrative the former slave Sancho returns to his home village but is inconsolable with grief when he finds his parents had been sold into slavery six years earlier. Later, when Arthur and Sancho are captured by Moors, Arthur is released but Sancho is unable to make an escape and rejoin his friend. Sancho's story, that had been so hopeful at the end of *Excursions of North America*, ends here and his ultimate fate is not revealed.

In *The Traveller in Africa* Priscilla highlights two colonisation schemes, one at Sierra Leone established by the African Association and the second at Bulama, (an island off what is now Guinea-Bissau), established by Mr Dalrymple and Captain Philip Beaver. The African settlements were intended to 'substitute, for that disgraceful traffic in slaves, a fair commerce with the inhabitants'.⁷⁰ In fact, Captain Beaver was 'an old and intimate friend'⁷¹ of Priscilla's son Edward. Much to Priscilla's disapproval he sponsored eleven year old Arthur Wakefield into an early entry into the navy.⁷² By 1825 Arthur was serving on the *Brazen* as part of a British Navy anti-slavery patrol off the West Coast of Africa. On one occasion, in charge of twenty-five men, he overtook a Spanish slaver in the ships boats, boarded the vessel, overcame the crew and freed 420 slaves. A year later he was given his first command the gin brig *Conflict* patrolling the full length of the West African slaving coast.⁷³ Following an illustrious thirty year naval career Arthur, like his brother William, became involved with the New Zealand Company colonisation scheme. He was appointed the Principal Agent for the Company's second settlement in Nelson. In 1843, as a result of a dispute with local Māori over the ownership of land in the Wairau Valley, Arthur and thirty European settlers, were

captured and killed. Arthur died from a tomahawk blow to the forehead. His brother William relayed the terrible news home in a letter sent initially to his clergyman brother-in-law.⁷⁴

The Traveller in Asia published in 1817 was Priscilla's final book. She states in the preface, 'I am induced to complete the series by the addition of a visit to Asia ; believing it to be a portion of the globe that contains many objects of peculiar interest, especially British India, where the dearest connexions of such numbers of our countrymen reside'.⁷⁵ Arthur Middleton had given up the idea of marriage, when his intended married another, and devoted his life instead to exploring foreign countries. He meets a new friend, Mr Melville, an English gentleman who had lived in India for some time and was familiar with the interior. He asks Arthur to take charge of his fourteen year old nephew Charles who becomes a companion just as Arthur had been to Henry Franklin in *Excursions in North America*. The book begins with Arthur recording his travels in a journal format but this later gives way to the stronger narrative of Charles interspersed with descriptive letters to his sister Adela. Probably reflecting the depth of material available to Priscilla the Indian section is significantly more expansive in detail than for China that begins in Pekin [*sic*] on page 210 of a volume consisting of 237 pages. Arthur has his usual exciting encounters with the country's wildlife in the form of snakes and tigers and an extended visit to a Hindoo [*sic*] village where he studied the religion, laws and customs. He reported in his journal:

The British territories are very extensive. Without being able to justify the measure of establishing colonies in a country to which we have no natural claim, I am induced to hope that the introduction of an improved code of laws, the gradual propagation of Christianity by the distribution of the Bible, and the effects of education on the children of the natives, will finally convert the innovation of ambition into a blessing ; and by gentle means

overturn the impious roles of Brahma, and substitute in their place the glorious light of the Gospel of Jesus Christ.⁷⁶

This seems a strange combination of messages: that Britain really has no business to be in India but, now it is, encouraging the spread of Christianity will make the Indians more like the British. This comment seems out of step with Priscilla's usual acceptance of cultural and religious differences. Has there been a change in the imperial world that Priscilla is reflecting, a subtle shift from 'not other' to 'other'? The book ends when Arthur returns young Charles to the care of his uncle in Calcutta and plans his own return to England. But Priscilla does not actually place him on board a ship or return him home creating an unresolved end for our fictional traveller Arthur Middleton.⁷⁷

From an examination of the themes of empire that are reflected in Priscilla's writings it is clear that each one is tempered with a form of qualification. Although she did not explicitly use the term British Empire in a wider sense, she acknowledged there were distant places that, through exploration and conquest, were connected to the metropole. The most obvious evidence of this relationship was useful and new products available to its citizens. But if these products had been produced by slaves, it was not acceptable to purchase them. The abolition message was a constant theme throughout her writings, from promoting the boycott of products, to the liberation of Sancho and the capture experience of Arthur Middleton. In colonies she saw opportunities for European settlers but also saw a lack of control over their use of land and their exploitation of indigenous peoples. Colonies are also portrayed as places of reinvention and personal redemption but, like the transported prisoner William Harrison, only for the individual prepared to change. As she sent the characters of her travel books further and further from the metropole she reflected, through the character Arthur Middleton, that the first-hand experience of empire was the domain of the single man on a personal journey of discovery. The role of the wider family and specifically the female

characters was passively to receive, without reply, male descriptions and impressions. Empire was something Priscilla incorporated into her writing in the way she viewed most things into her life, totally based upon her own moral perspective. She did not question that Britain should have an empire but did not hesitate to criticise where she saw injustice. Priscilla Wakefield's values were firmly focussed on her desire for the equality of individuals, wherever their place in the world.

For all Priscilla's methods to improve the child, what is clear is that her grandson Edward Gibbon was a difficult student. She provided guidance in her kind and gentle way but as a result of his selfish and impulsive nature his life took an irretrievable turn with his conviction and prison term. What, if anything, can be discerned of Priscilla's influence on her grandson's writings? In the first instance, her eclectic interests, that ranged from entomology to economics, backed up with an extensive library, must have set some example to the young child. Her interest in the writings of Adam Smith, whom she quotes on the first page of *Reflections on the Present State of the Female Sex*, has an interesting parallel: between 1835 and 1843, Edward Gibbon published an edition of Smith's *Wealth of Nations* with comments by himself and others in four volumes.⁷⁸

In their respective views of colonisation we can see differences: Priscilla appearing to take a neutral position on the topic of colonial policy and expressing her views at the level of the individual, praising Quaker William Penn but criticising the actions of people she called 'unprincipled adventurers'. In his writings, thirty years later, Edward Gibbon's very use of the words 'systematic colonisation' signals something planned, controlled and aimed at managing social, economic and political variables to promote a new form of colonial experience, for both colonies and the metropole. As Olssen states, 'whereas classical political economy, from Smith to David Ricardo, rejected colonisation, Wakefield proved them wrong and stood the tradition on its head, thus deducing from political economy the foundation for a

second British Empire based on trade.⁷⁹ Edward Gibbon would also depart from his grandmother's views on the merits of transportation and while the fictional characters that Priscilla sent into the empire were single men, in Edward Gibbon's colonisation proposals, 'the immigrants conveyed to the Colony ... shall consist entirely of *young* married or marriageable persons *of both sexes in equal numbers*'.⁸⁰

However, it is possibly in the area of style that we see Priscilla's greatest influence on Edward Gibbon in the wide reading of subject matter, detailed descriptions of places extracted from other sources, a persuasive style and most importantly, an attractive format. His reading habits are described in 'Facts Relating to The Punishment of Death in the Metropolis' where he stated, 'for, whilst in Newgate, I had occasion to read with care every book concerning New South Wales and Van Dieman's Land, as well as a long series of newspapers published in those colonies'.⁸¹ The epistolary form favoured by Priscilla, was adopted in *A Letter from Sydney* and 'A View of the Art of Colonization', where there is an exchange of correspondence between a colonist and a statesman with Edward Gibbon assuming the persona of the colonist. The medium provided an entry point for the message, and as interested parties took up and promoted the ideas of systematic colonisation, Edward Gibbon, in some quarters, was able to claw back a semblance of respectability following his release from Newgate.

In her travel books Priscilla aimed to encourage children to extend their knowledge of the world. She did this by developing family characters, travel scenarios and including maps to encourage a dynamic interaction between the child reader and the factual information of the text. The significance of her decision to base the fictional Middleton family on the Wakefield grandchildren has not been previously highlighted. The poignancy of that interface between fiction and fact is that Priscilla's literary excursions were written from the safety of her home, the characters rescued from any danger and safely returned to family and friends.

Yet within a generation, the Wakefield family itself would face a colonial reality that involved loss, separation and not-so-happy endings.

Notes

- [1] MacKenzie, General Editor's Foreword, vii.
- [2] Hunt, *An Introduction to Children's Literature*, 29. Examples of research in this area are: Bratton, 'Of England, Home and Duty the Image of England in Victorian and Edwardian Juvenile Fiction', 73-93; Gordon-Craig, 'Children's Adventure Stories & the Ideals of Empire'; Kutzer, *Empire's Children*; Richards, ed. *Imperialism and Juvenile Literature*.
- [3] Levine, *The British Empire*, 43.
- [4] Wakefield, Edward Gibbon, 'A View of the Art of Colonization', 779.
- [5] Edward Gibbon, his brothers Arthur, William, Daniel and Felix all died in New Zealand as did Edward Gibbon's only son, Edward Jerningham. *Edward Gibbon Wakefield and the Colonial Dream*, vii.
- [6] For example, compare, Fairburn, 'Wakefield, Edward Gibbon 1796-1862'; Moss, 'Wakefield, Edward Gibbon (1796-1862)'.
- [7] 'While Wakefield has gained some respectability elsewhere, this has not occurred in New Zealand. ... We may have to take Wakefield more seriously than this. He was not a reactionary conservative, he was an important Radical reformer who shifted colonial policy in a new direction. ... Whatever his personal failings, his vision and his interventions are too important to the foundation of New Zealand colonial society to be dismissed or ignored.' Martin, 'A "Small Nation on the Move"', 108.
- [8] Wakefield, Priscilla, *Variety*, [iii]-iv.

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- [9] Hill, 'Priscilla Wakefield as a Writer of Children's Educational Books', 10-11. During the course of their marriage her husband lost the family business and failed in numerous ventures. [He] 'seems in fact to have been entirely lacking, not only in business capacity, ... but also in the strength of mind to meet misfortune bravely, or bear it patiently'. *Some Family Records of Daniel Bell of Tottenham*, [Journal] 7-8.
- [10] Extracts from Priscilla's journal collected and edited by Lady Chapman as a TS manuscript are bound together with the memoirs of her brother Jonathan and held in the Alexander Turnbull Library in Wellington, New Zealand. It has the title *Some Family Records of Daniel Bell of Tottenham*.
- [11] For biographical information on Priscilla Wakefield see, Aindow, 'Priscilla Wakefield (1751-1832)'; Shteir, 'Wakefield [née Bell], Priscilla (1750-1832)'.
- [12] Priscilla Wakefield's son Edward (1774-1854) wrote *An Account of Ireland, Statistical and Political*, grandson Edward Gibbon Wakefield was the author of numerous works that discussed social concerns and promoted his theory of colonisation, his son, and Priscilla's great-grandson, Edward Jerningham Wakefield (1820-1879) wrote *Adventure in New Zealand* that describes his time in New Zealand from 1839 to 1844.
- [13] For example, Dougal, 'Teaching Conduct or Telling a New Tale?'; Hill, 'Priscilla Wakefield as a Writer of Children's Educational Books'; Kroeg, 'Class Mobility'; Labbe, "'A Species of Knowledge both Useful and Ornamental'", 35-50; Shteir, *Cultivating Women, Cultivating Science*, 83-89; Smith, 'Slavery, Abolition, and the Nation in Priscilla Wakefield's Tour Books for Children'.
- [14] Avery, *Nineteenth Century Children*, 13.
- [15] *Ibid.*, 28.

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- [16] For example, one of the Strickland sisters, Catharine Parr Traill (née Strickland 1802-1899), wrote a number of moral children's books between 1819 and 1831. Following her marriage she emigrated to Canada and wrote her most well known book *The Backwoods of Canada* published in 1836. Although for an adult audience the epistolary format, consisting of eighteen descriptive letters to family in England plus a map, parallels the style Priscilla used in *Excursions in North America*. A New Zealand example is Lady Mary Ann Barker who wrote *Station Life in New Zealand* published in 1870 that was written as a series of letters to a sister in England.
- [17] Darton, *Children's Books in England*, 168.
- [18] Avery, *Nineteenth Century Children*, 14-15.
- [19] Shteir, 'Priscilla Wakefield's Books', 95.
- [20] For the sake of brevity the full titles of Wakefield's books have not been included in the text.
- [21] Wakefield, Priscilla, *Leisure Hours*, vol 1, iii.
- [22] The name of this Seneca chief can be found written in a number of ways but phonetically as Kayashota. For biographical information see Abler, 'Kayashota'.
- [23] Wakefield, Priscilla, *Leisure Hours*, vol. 2, 48.
- [24] *Ibid.*, 51.
- [25] Wakefield, Priscilla, *Excursions in North America*, 15.
- [26] For a detailed discussion see, Smith, 'Slavery, Abolition, and the Nation in Priscilla Wakefield's Tour Books for Children'.
- [27] Wakefield, Priscilla, *Mental Improvement*, 161-162.
- [28] *Ibid.*, 167.
- [29] *Ibid.*, 169.

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- [30] Midgley, *Feminism and Empire*, 43. A contemporary writer of Priscilla's, Maria Edgeworth noted, 'twenty-five thousand people in England have absolutely left off eating West India sugar, from the hope that when there is no longer any demand for sugar the slaves will not be so cruelly treated.' Darton, *Children's Books in England*, 156.
- [31] *Some Family Records of Daniel Bell of Tottenham*, [Journal] 32. For discussion on Priscilla's *Reflections* see Dimand, 'An Eighteenth-Century English Feminist Response to Political Economy'.
- [32] Hill, 'Priscilla Wakefield as a Writer of Children's Educational Books', 5.
- [33] *Some Family Records of Daniel Bell of Tottenham*, [Journal] 106.
- [34] 'Her travel books were easily her most popular productions, the first one reaching nineteen editions by the year 1850'. Dougal, 'Teaching Conduct or Telling a New Tale?', 300.
- [35] Folded maps are also included in works of Priscilla's son Edward, grandson Edward Gibbon and great-grandson Edward Jerningham.
- [36] *An Introduction to Botany*, published in 1796, was the first time Priscilla had used the epistolary style in letters between sisters Felica and Constance. But Constance was already on holiday with her aunt.
- [37] Labbe, "'A Species of Knowledge Both Useful and Ornamental'", 39-40. Kroeg, 'Class Mobility', 28.
- [38] 'Here, Wakefield allows one young woman, the very model for her female readers, to reach to the outermost, near-to-forbidden limits for potential, before Wakefield finally retreats and firmly reasserts her conventional ideals.' Dougal, 'Teaching Conduct or Telling a New Tale?', 317.

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- [39] This trend is evident in the three travel books related to Europe and Britain. In *The Juvenile Travellers* Laura wrote seventeen letters to Sophia and Sophia wrote six to Laura. In *A Family Tour* only Arthur and Edwin are the letter writers and in *Perambulations in London* of the forty-three letters only one was written by a female character Catherine to her cousin Emma. In the books about North America, Africa and Asia all the letters are written by the male travellers.
- [40] This possibility is also noted by Kroeg, 'Class Mobility', 29.
- [41] Wakefield, Priscilla, *A Family Tour*, 241.
- [42] Wakefield, Priscilla, *The Traveller in Asia*, 9.
- [43] Wakefield, Priscilla, *Excursions in North America*, [iii].
- [44] Ibid., [1].
- [45] Ibid., 19.
- [46] Ibid., 73.
- [47] Ibid., 74. Sancho's wife is acquired by a lady in Charleston who was 'going to set the noble example of giving freedom to her negros'.
- [48] Ibid., 169.
- [49] Ibid., 420. See Smith, 'Slavery, Abolition, and the Nation in Priscilla Wakefield's Tour Books for Children' for a detailed discussion about the character Sancho.
- [50] Bradford, 'The End of Empire?', 92.
- [51] Colley, *Captives*, 49-50.
- [52] Wakefield, Priscilla, *Excursions in North America*, 2.
- [53] Ibid., 205.
- [54] Ibid., 80.
- [55] Ibid.
- [56] Ibid., 81.

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- [57] Wakefield, Edward Gibbon, *Plan of a Company*, 282-283.
- [58] ‘Instructions to Colonel Wakefield, Principal Agent of the Company’, 7F.
- [59] N.Z. Waitangi Tribunal. *Te Whanganui A Tara Me Ona Takiwa*, 47.
- [60] Wakefield, Edward Jerningham. *Adventure in New Zealand*, 63.
- [61] Temple, *A Sort of Conscience*, 408.
- [62] Wakefield, Priscilla, *Sketches of Human Manners*, 225-226.
- [63] For a description of the events and trials see Temple, *A Sort of Conscience*, 89-111.
For his part in the crime Edward Gibbon’s brother William was imprisoned in Lancaster Castle for three years.
- [64] ‘Penn wrote continuously and voluminously in Newgate, turning out three long tracts that we know of, as well as several epistles. Throughout them all runs the single theme of liberty of conscience.’ Peare, *William Penn*, 133.
- [65] Wakefield, Edward Gibbon, *A Letter from Sydney*, 55. In 1829 Priscilla was about 78 years old her health was so poor that in 1822, when her grand daughter Catherine married, Priscilla was not told until after the event and then could only smile. Temple, *A Sort of Conscience*, 76.
- [66] Wakefield, Edward Gibbon, *A Letter from Sydney*, 55.
- [67] *Some Family Records of Daniel Bell of Tottenham*, [Journal], 124.
- [68] Wakefield, Priscilla, *The Traveller in Africa*, [v].
- [69] *Ibid.*, 4.
- [70] *Ibid.*, 344.
- [71] Temple, *A Sort of Conscience*, 44.
- [72] At Arthur’s intended entry into the navy Priscilla wrote. ‘Edward proposes to send dear Arthur to sea with Captain Beevor and enter him into the navy. A line of life I

entirely disapprove. To part with him on such an errand is no small trial'. *Some Family Records of Daniel Bell of Tottenham*, [Journal] 121.

- [73] Temple, *A Sort of Conscience*, 87-88.
- [74] *Ibid.*, 321-322.
- [75] Wakefield, Priscilla, *The Traveller in Asia*, [iii].
- [76] *Ibid.*, 9.
- [77] In the introduction to *The Traveller in Africa* it is stated Arthur 'intended to go to Africa, Asia and South America'. The uncompleted South American journey may have been the intended point of resolution for Arthur Middleton.
- [78] Prichard, *The Collected Works of Edward Gibbon Wakefield*, 33-34. Historian Erik Olssen notes that in her collection of Wakefield's works Prichard cites the edition of Smith's work but does not include any text. He argues, 'this work is central to any intellectual biography of Wakefield; it shows the extent and depth of his grasp of the central issues in classical political economy.' Olssen, 'Mr Wakefield and New Zealand as an Experiment in Post-Enlightenment Experimental Practice', 205.
- [79] Olssen, 'Wakefield and the Scottish Enlightenment', 48.
- [80] Wakefield, Edward Gibbon, 'Plan of a Company', 276.
- [81] Wakefield, Edward Gibbon, 'Facts Relating to the Punishment of Death in the Metropolis', 266.

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